

Chemical Examination of the Seeds of *Psoralea Corylifolia*, Linn. Part I.

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The plant *Psoralea corylifolia* thrives all over India and its seeds have enjoyed an honoured place in Ayurvedic medicine, particularly for the treatment of skin diseases, such as leucoderma (Nadkarni, "The Indian Materia Medica," 1927, p. 717 ; Chopra, "Indigenous Drugs of India," 1933, pp. 367-373). The seeds contain an essential oil with a persistent odour and are used locally in the preparation of certain types of medicated oils and incense preparations.

Menon (*J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1910, **29**, 1431) obtained the fatty oil from the seeds and determined some of its physical and chemical constants. Sen, Chatterjee and Dutta (Chopra, *loc. cit.*) in 1923, isolated an unsaponifiable oil of the formula $C_{17}H_{24}O$ (b.p. 180-190/11-15 mm.), a yellow acidic compound ($C_{40}H_{45}O_{11}$) (?) and a methylglucoside. The next chemical investigation was carried out by Chopra and Chatterjee (*Ind. J. Med. Res.*, 1927-28, **15**, 49) mainly for purposes of pharmacological study and found the essential oil to be the active principle. They recommend an oleo-resinous extract for the treatment of skin diseases. The present paper contains the results of a detailed analysis of the chemical constituents of the seeds.

Preliminary Examination.

50 G. of the crushed seeds were extracted successively with the following solvents and the extracts were dried at 100°.*

Petroleum ether (b.p. 40°-60°)	...	10.95%
Ethyl ether	...	8.80
Chloroform	...	3.70
Ethyl acetate	...	3.05
Alcohol	...	8.30

	Total	34.70

* The above results vary in certain respects from those recorded by Chopra and Chatterjee (*loc. cit.*).

The petroleum ether extract was found to consist of a dark reddish-brown viscous oil. The ethyl ether extract was composed mainly of the resinous constituents to which the colour of the seeds may be ascribed. No definite conclusions could be drawn regarding the nature of the constituents of the other extracts.

The seeds were tested with Prollius fluid for alkaloids. The results were negative. Alkaloidal assays by standard methods also failed to give any indication of the presence of alkaloidal constituents in the seeds. When distilled with steam, the seeds yielded 0.05% of a pale yellow volatile oil with a strong aromatic odour. An aqueous extract of the seeds gave tests for the presence of small amounts of reducing sugars and considerable amounts of hydrolysable polysaccharides. Starch and tannin were absent. Evidence was obtained regarding the presence of an enzyme in the seeds.

The Petroleum Ether Extract.

A genuine sample of the seeds was obtained from the local bazaar and 10 kg. were crushed and extracted with petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°) in a large Soxhlet. When the solvent was evaporated 1 kg. of the oil was obtained. This oil, on standing for a few days, deposited a pale yellow crystalline material (2.5% of the oil). The oil was decanted and the solid was washed with a small quantity of cold petroleum ether and purified.

The fatty oil thus obtained had the following constants.

Specific gravity	...	0.9692 at 25°
Refractive index	...	1.5132 at 25°
*Saponification value	...	117.20
Iodine value (Hanus)	...	96.9
*Acetyl value	...	96.3
*Acid value	...	19.9
Reichert-Meisel value	...	1.5
Insoluble acids (fatty acids and resin acids)	...	69.0%
Unsaponifiable matter	...	27.0%

* These and other similar values of highly coloured substances were determined by titration in a two phase medium according to a modification of the Albert method (*Mys. Univ. J.*, 1930, 4, 241).

The oil was saponified with potassium hydroxide. The resulting soap, after extraction with ether to obtain the unsaponifiable matter, was dissolved in water and acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid, when the insoluble acids were liberated. A quantitative estimation according to Twitchell's gravimetric method showed that resin acids formed 21.5% of the mixed acids. After the removal of the resin acids, the fatty acids were separated into their saturated and unsaturated components by Twitchell's lead salt method (*Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1921, 13, 806).

The total mixed acids had the following chemical constants.

Mean mol. wt.	...	378.6
Iodine value (Hanus)	...	108.4
<i>Insoluble fatty acids.</i>	...	78.0%
Mean mol. wt. of fatty acids	...	337.0
Iodine value (Hanus)	...	125.7
<i>Saturated fatty acids.</i>	...	18.6% of the mixed acids.
Mean mol. wt. of saturated fatty acids	...	294.5
Iodine value (Hanus)	...	3.5

The main bulk of the mixed acids was dissolved in 95% alcohol and subjected to the separation of solid and liquid acids according to the method of Twitchell, when along with the granular precipitate of the lead salts of the solid acids, most of the resin separated as a dark brown viscous mass. The granular precipitate was filtered off, washed with alcohol and ether and reprecipitated from alcoholic solution; it was thus completely freed from resin. The unsaturated acids were recovered from the alcoholic filtrates (mol. wt., 320; iodine value, 157.5).

The unsaturated acids.—The unsaturated acids were very highly coloured, possibly owing to the incomplete separation of resin acids. They were converted into the methyl esters and the latter distilled under reduced pressure (1 mm.), when they passed over between 168°.177° as a pale brown oil.* A portion of the acids liberated from this was treated with bromine according to the method of Eibner and Muggenthaler (Lewkowitsch, "Chemical Technology

* The esters were obtained in 5 different fractions whose iodine value gradually increased from 120.2 to 147.2, and the mean mol. wt. from 272 to 277 (cf. Jois and Manjunath, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 7, 523).

and Analysis of Oils, Fats and Waxes'', 6th Ed. Vol. I, p. 585). A small quantity of colourless ether insoluble additive compound separated. This melted at 177-78° and dissolved completely in benzene and after repeated crystallisations melted at 183.5° and proved to be hexabromostearic acid. (Found: Br, 63.4. $C_{18}H_{30}O_2Br_6$ requires Br, 63.3 per cent). This indicated the presence of a small amount of linolenic acid in the unsaturated acids. From the ether soluble additive compounds tetrabromostearic acid (m.p. 113-14°) was isolated.

Another portion of the mixed liquid acids from the methyl esters was oxidised by cold dilute alkaline permanganate and from the mixture of insoluble hydroxy acids dihydroxystearic acid (m.p. 130-31°, mol. wt. 316.4) and tetrahydroxystearic acid (m.p. 156°, mol. wt. 348.4) were isolated. From the mother liquors of the oxidation mixture a small quantity of hexahydroxystearic acid (m.p. 173°, mol. wt. 381.5) was obtained.

The above results establish the presence of oleic and linolic acid and a small quantity of linolenic acid among the unsaturated acids.

The saturated acids.—The solid acids, obtained by Twitchell's method of separation were slightly coloured. They were converted into the methyl esters (50 g.) and fractionally distilled at 1 mm. pressure.

Fraction No.	Range of Temperature.	Wt. of fraction.	Mean mol. wt. of acids from the saponification value.
1	150-152°	22.80	251.4
2	152-155°	4.46	255.4
3	155-158°	1.10	256.5
4	158-162°	4.00	266.7
5	162-164°	0.55	268.0
6	164-172°	3.45	271.8
7	172-181°	1.23	277.2
8	181-182°	1.69	280.3
9	Residue	10.10	362.0

Pure palmitic acid (m. p. 61°, mol. wt. 257.8) was isolated from the first three fractions. Its *p*-phenylphenacyl ester was

prepared according to Drake and Bronitsky (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 52, 3715) and was found to melt at 94°. (Found: C, 80.07; H, 9.21. $C_{30}H_{42}O_3$ requires C, 79.95; H, 9.4 per cent).

From fractions 4 to 7 about 2 g. of pure stearic acid (m.p. 68.4°, mol. wt. 285.1) was isolated. Its *p*-phenylphenacyl ester melted at 97.5°. (Found: C, 80.37; H, 9.71. $C_{32}H_{46}O_3$ requires C, 80.26; H, 9.69 per cent). The mother liquors of stearic acid gave a fraction melting at 58-59° having the mol. wt. 263.

The residue (9) was highly coloured. It was saponified and the liberated acid was treated with animal charcoal and crystallised from 95% alcohol. It melted at 75-76° and had the mol. wt. 368.1. It did not depress the m.p. of a pure sample of lignoceric acid from another source. Repeated recrystallisations from various solvents did not raise the melting point. An attempt to obtain a specimen having a higher m.p. by the partial precipitation of the lithium salt according to Holde and Godbole (*Ber.*, 1926, 59, 39) was unsuccessful. Its identity was confirmed by comparing its *p*-phenylphenacyl ester with that of pure lignoceric acid melting at 102°. (Found: C, 81.14; H, 10.4. $C_{38}H_{58}O_3$ requires C, 81.07; H, 10.39 per cent).

The unsaponifiable matter consisted of a dark brown viscous mass and contained principally neutral resin bodies. However, it gave the colour reactions of sterols but no pure compound could be isolated even by digitonin treatment.

The crystalline solid, deposited on keeping the oil for some time, was found to melt at 135° (*cf.* Chopra and Chatterjee, *loc. cit.*). From this material on repeated crystallisations from dilute alcohol a pure compound melting at 162° was isolated as the main constituent. This substance was found to have the formula $C_{11}H_6O_3$. [Found: C, 71.01; H, 3.20. M. W. (in benzene by the cryoscopic method), 182. $C_{11}H_6O_3$ requires C, 70.94; H, 3.25 per cent; M. W., 186). It has been named *Psoralen*.

Psoralen is sparingly soluble in cold petroleum ether and ether but dissolves readily in alcohol and chloroform. It can be crystallised in long silky needles from boiling water in which it is slightly soluble. It is insoluble in cold dilute sodium carbonate or sodium hydroxide, but when heated dissolves readily. The material is precipitated unchanged on acidifying. Preliminary investigations have indicated that it is possibly a coumaron-coumarin. Further work is in progress regarding its constitution and the results will be communicated in a subsequent paper.

SUMMARY.

The petroleum ether extract of the seeds of *Psoralea corylifolia* gave a dark reddish-brown oil and a crystalline solid $C_{11}H_6O_3$ now named *Psoralen*, melting at 162° . The oil was found to contain a considerable amount of resin. The fatty acids obtained from the oil were found to be principally palmitic, oleic and linolic acids together with small amounts of stearic, lignoceric and linolenic acids.

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